

ISic3458

I.Sicily inscription 3458

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone; bronze

Object

pavement

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Excavations on decumanus maximums 1999-2011, Capo Boeo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 644935

Bibliography

Silvestrini, M. 2014. Nuove epigrafi da Lilibeo. In Zaccaria, C.(eds.), *L'Epigrafia dei porti. Atti della XVIIe recncontre sur l'épigraphie du monde romain, Aquileia, 14-16 ottobre 2010*. Trieste. pp. 207-226. At 215-220 no.3b fig.9

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3458. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388608>